

“Exposure Assessment in Methymercury (MeHg)”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Methylmercury (MeHg) is by far the most common organic form of mercury in the food chain. The largest source of mercury exposure for most people in developed countries is inhalation of mercury vapour due to the continuous release of elemental mercury from dental amalgam. Exposure to methylmercury mostly occurs via the diet. Methylmercury collects and concentrates especially in the aquatic food chain, making populations with a high intake of fish and seafood particularly vulnerable.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.3.2. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary methylmercury intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) of 1.6 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary methylmercury exposure.

Mean dietary methylmercury exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.215 and 1.042 µg/kg b.w. per week for mean and P95, respectively. It was found that about 2.5 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 1.6 µg/Kg b.w. per week. Higher exposure was observed for infants and other children due to their lower body weight and may be due to their consumption habits, especially in the cases with higher fish consumption.

There was no significant difference in methylmercury intake between genders and different geographical areas.

Sea bream (26.8%), canned tuna (23.0%), swordfish (7.0%) and salmons (6.1%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the methylmercury intake.

2 Introduction

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2.1 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary methylmercury intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) of 1.6 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary methylmercury exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

Mercury occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2008-2022. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Occurrence results below the LOD were set to zero for the Low-bound scenario, half the LOD for the Middle-bound scenario and LOD for the Upper-bound scenario. Concentrations for mercury in human milk were taken from EFSA's opinion. The aggregated concentration values for fish meat were calculated by excluding the data for large fish as tuna, sharks and swordfish. All of the data on mercury were measured as total mercury, so the following assumptions were used: in fish, out of the total Hg, 20% is iHg and 100% is MeHg; in crustaceans and molluscs, out of the total Hg, 50% is iHg and 80% is MeHg; in foods other than fish and seafood, all mercury is iHg.

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264).

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 14.0 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Methylmercury (MeHg) summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.3.2

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Methylmercury (MeHg)
Substance Category	Contaminant
Reference value	1.6 µg/Kg b.w. per week
Type of reference value	Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Methylmercury (MeHg)

Scenario				
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	
Min	0	0	0	
Max	19.814	19.814	19.814	
Mean	0.211	0.215	0.218	
SD	0.634	0.636	0.638	
P25	0	0	0	
Median	0	0	0	
P75	0.176	0.182	0.192	
P95	1.042	1.042	1.042	
pctOver	2.5%	2.5%	2.6%	

* pctOver:Percentage of population above the reference value

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.215 and 1.042 µg/kg b.w. per week (Table 4.2). It was found that overall 2.5 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 1.6 µg/Kg b.w. per week, as also shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
FEMALE	0	19.814	0.171	0.515	0	0	0.174	0.928	1.7%
MALE	0	18.821	0.260	0.738	0	0	0.276	1.379	3.4%

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is a difference between the two genders showing different fish consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Ammochostos	0	5.702	0.228	0.514	0	0	0.276	1.715	5.2%
Larnaka	0	6.678	0.275	0.928	0	0	0.160	1.340	3.5%
Lefkosia	0	18.821	0.207	0.513	0	0	0.212	1.066	1.2%
Lemesos	0	19.814	0.178	0.581	0	0	0.125	0.928	3.1%
Pafos	0	3.390	0.198	0.463	0	0	0.267	1.344	1.7%

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Adolescents	0	2.927	0.207	0.461	0	0	0.156	1.340	3.4%
Adults	0	6.678	0.196	0.571	0	0	0.179	0.928	1.8%
Elderly	0	3.723	0.139	0.424	0	0	0.097	0.665	1.9%
Infants	0	18.821	0.171	1.343	0	0	0.000	0.265	1.9%
Other children	0	5.706	0.389	0.792	0	0	0.488	1.868	6.4%
Toddlers	0	19.814	0.505	1.638	0	0	0.260	3.178	8.4%

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that toddlers and other children had higher exposure (2 or 3 times) than the other population classes. The lower body weight of these population classes is the main reason for the higher exposure. Also 8.4 % toddlers and 6.4% of the infants, were exceeding the TWI for methylmercury intake. Investigating the consumption data, it was observed that the

exceedance of the TWI in some cases in these population classes was affected by the high consumption of fish.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population class]

Figure 4.6 illustrates the mean exposure to mercury by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in some population classes, but for infants, toddlers and other children were important differences between the geographical areas. This is because of the different fish consumption habits in the population classes between the different areas in Cyprus.

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total mercury exposure is shown in Figure 4.7. Sea bream (26.8%), canned tuna (23.0%), swordfish (7.0%) and salmons (6.1%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the methylmercury intake. It is well known that mercury mostly occurs large fish species. These fish species are also highly consumed by all population classes, so they present a significant contribution to the mercury dietary intake.

Figure 4.7 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 5

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Methylmercury (MeHg) Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Methylmercury (MeHg) Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 5 with greater than 0.5% contribution

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Level5	Contribution
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Fish (meat)	Fish (meat)	Fish (meat)	2.55%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Level5	Contribution
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Freshwater fish	Miscellaneous freshwater fishes	Catfishes (freshwater)	0.96%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Freshwater fish	Miscellaneous freshwater fishes	Perch	2.17%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Diadromous fish	Salmons, trouts, smelts	Smelt	0.74%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Diadromous fish	Salmons, trouts, smelts	Salmons	6.06%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	Sea bass	1.83%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	Sea bream	26.85%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	Bogue	0.52%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	Mullets	2.02%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Miscellaneous demersal marine fishes	Anglerfish, monkfish and stargazers	4.63%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Level5	Contribution
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Flounders, halibuts, soles	Turbot	1.92%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Miscellaneous pelagic marine fishes	Garfish	0.52%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Cods, hakes, haddocks	Cod	1.22%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Tunas, bonitos, billfishes	Swordfish	7.00%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Sharks, rays, chimaeras	Sharks	1.00%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish offal	Fish roe	Fish roe	Fish roe	1.21%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Crustaceans	Shrimps and prawns	Shrimps and prawns	Shrimps and prawns	2.77%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Crustaceans	Shrimps and prawns	Shrimps, common	Shrimps, common	1.04%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Molluscs	Squids, cuttlefishes, octopuses	Octopuses	Octopus, common	0.76%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Level5	Contribution
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Molluscs	Squids, cuttlefishes, octopuses	Squids	Squids	4.58%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish and seafood processed	Processed or preserved fish (including processed offal)	Canned/jarred fish	Canned tunas and similar	22.96%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish and seafood processed	Processed or preserved fish (including processed offal)	Structured/textured fish meat products or fish paste	Fish fingers, breaded	3.22%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish and seafood processed	Processed or preserved fish (including processed offal)	Structured/textured fish meat products or fish paste	Fish paste or surimi	0.57%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of methylmercury has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure to methylmercury.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the preparation of occurrence data	+/-
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as MeHg concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with an ICP-MS method in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumptions taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence data (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean dietary methylmercury exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.215 and 1.042 µg/kg b.w. per week for mean and P95, respectively. It was found that about 2.5 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 1.6 µg/Kg b.w. per week. Higher exposure was observed for infants and other children due to their lower body weight and may be due to their consumption habits, especially in the cases with higher fish consumption.

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7 References

1. EFSA. 2011b. Evaluation of the FoodEx, the food classification system applied to the development of the EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database. EFSA Journal 2011; 9(3):1970. [27 pp.] doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2011.1970.
2. EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM). Scientific Opinion on the risk for public health related to the presence of mercury and methylmercury in food. EFSA Journal 2012;10(12):2985 [241 pp.] doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2012.2985.
3. EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2006. Guidance of the Scientific Committee on a request from EFSA related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. The EFSA Journal. 438, 1-54.

8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight

Key	Description
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices